

Icebreaker One

Delivering an effective National Data
Library

1. Clarify the problem the National Data Library is designed to address

A clear vision is a necessary design constraint for the National Data Library (NDL).

During the 2024 election, the [Labour Party manifesto](#) described that the NDL will “bring together existing research programmes and help deliver data-driven public services, whilst maintaining strong safeguards and ensuring all of the public benefit”. Science and Technology minister Peter Kyle [has said the NDL will be](#) a “data access policy and a library and exchange service” and will deliver “AI-powered public services that [citizens] deserve”.

[This ambiguous language has caused confusion](#). As a result, there seems to be (at least) two competing visions for what the NDL could do:

1. Enable improved use of government-held data for research.
2. Enable improved operational data access across public services.

The difference between data for *research* and data for *operations* is a significant one, technically, legally and commercially. In health, the [NHS Federated Data Platform](#) is designed to connect data from across NHS organisations to assist healthcare professionals in real-time, operational decision-making. There’s also a need for a much wider set of data infrastructures to ensure health data is safely used for research.

The needs of researchers and operational data users are unlikely to be met by a singular intervention. We recommend the UK Government and other organisations looking to influence its design clarify their vision for the NDL, documenting this as a clear, tightly-bound [problem statement](#). This will help bridge the chasm between a high-level political vision and technical execution.

In this Technical White Paper, we’re choosing to pursue a vision of a NDL that enables improved discovery of government-held data for research. This is in line with the Challenge’s description of the NDL’s purpose to “make public sector datasets more accessible to researchers and enable future science to thrive”.

(The UK has significant improvements to make on operational data access, though. Estonia’s [X-Road](#) is an example of modern cross-government data sharing to deliver more efficient public services. This is sometimes referred to as the [‘data exchange layer’](#) in Digital Public Infrastructure circles.)

2. Take inspiration from existing research data infrastructures, rather than a metaphor

The term 'library' isn't very helpful. It suggests a lot of books or files (data) being brought together into a central place. This isn't how the web works.

We think it's more useful for the UK Government and others to take design inspiration for the NDL from existing research data infrastructures. This includes data infrastructures that:

- *Improve discovery and search of data that's available for research.* E.g. [data.gov.uk](#), [gov.uk API Catalogue](#), [Administrative Data Research UK Data Catalogue](#), [HDR UK Gateway](#), [Google Dataset Search](#), [Open Net Zero](#), [Rail Data Marketplace](#), [Data for London Library](#).
- *Host data and make it openly/widely accessible for research.* E.g. [Eurostat Data](#), [Hugging Face](#), [Registry of Open Data on AWS](#), [London Datastore](#).
- *Provide a secure environment for access to sensitive data for research, based on common, standardised and/or tiered researcher accreditation.* E.g. [UK Data Service](#), [ONS Secure Research Service](#), [OpenSAFELY](#), [Data and Analytics Research Environments \(DARE\) UK](#).
- *Provide access to sensitive data for research, based on a bespoke application process, governance and access procedures.* E.g. [INSIGHT](#), [Research Data Scotland](#).
- *Provide access to linked or combined datasets from across multiple organisations for research.* E.g. [Clinical Practice Research Datalink](#), [ONS Integrated Data Service](#), [Système National des Données de Santé \(SNDS\)](#), [UK Longitudinal Linkage Collaboration](#), [Scottish CivTech Challenge 10.4](#).
- *Generate new datasets for research.* E.g. [Genomics England](#), [UK Biobank](#), [Smart Data Research UK](#).
- *Enable access to privately-held data for research.* E.g. [Common European Data Spaces](#), [Greater London Authority's High Streets Data Service](#), [National Underground Asset Register](#), [Stream](#).
- *Drive development, adoption and/or enforcement of common data standards and practices.* E.g. [Health Data Research UK Alliance](#), [International Data Spaces Association](#), [UK Data Standards Authority](#).

- *Provide access to compute, data science tools and other software for researchers to work with data.* E.g. [AWS Data Exchange](#).
- *Provide community for researchers and drive opportunities for collaboration around data.* E.g. [Github](#), [Kaggle](#).
- *Provide access to learning materials and drive reuse of other artefacts produced by research (such as methods, analysis scripts and publications).* E.g. [ADR UK Online Learning Hub](#), [European Open Science Cloud](#).

In reality, most data infrastructures perform multiple roles. And many of the data infrastructures listed above work together to serve researchers' needs. For example, Administrative Data Research UK and the ONS Secure Research Service [are tightly connected](#).

3. Ensure the NDL adds something new, or improves or replaces what already exists

The UK's research data ecosystem is crowded. Many of the data infrastructures listed above are already maintained or supported by the UK Government.

The UK Government uses different channels to coordinate, fund and otherwise support the development of research data infrastructures. It does a lot of this work through [UK Research and Innovation](#) (UKRI) and by sector, via organisations like [Health Data Research UK](#) and the [Economic and Social Research Council](#) (ESRC). In its [Data Infrastructure Strategy 2022-2027](#), the ESRC says that it has spent more than £200m in data collection, creation, curation and delivery.

There are various groups across UK Government seeking to improve government data infrastructure, including [Essential Shared Data Assets](#), [Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group](#), [Data Linkage Champion Network](#) and [Responsible Technology Adoption Unit](#). The [DSIT Central Digital and Data Office](#) has a [new independent panel](#) to shape the government's 'digital centre' and [is working on a Data Marketplace](#). We understand the Catapults, part-funded by UK Government, are proposing to operate a 'Data Sharing Infrastructure Hub' to promote cross-sector data sharing.

"Don't build a new thing unless you definitely, absolutely, must" is Ellie Ashman's recommendation for the NDL, based on [her experience with the Government Digital Service's work on registers](#). We agree. To be effective among existing data infrastructure, the NDL will need to:

- Address a gap in what already exists, or;
- Add to / promote / amplify what already exists, or;
- Replace or consolidate what already exists.

We urge the team responsible for delivery of the NDL - and organisations proposing how it could work - to base their work on an understanding of the UK's existing research data infrastructure. Intended users should be engaged early, to understand the needs not met by existing data infrastructures.

4. Deliver a National Data Library to improve discovery of research data held by the public sector

So what role could the NDL play? And how could it be delivered technically?

In the spirit of the Technical White Paper Challenge, we are offering a feasible implementation option here. Others have made higher-order contributions that we second, such as the need for the NDL to be '[consensual, safe, and transparent](#)' and [to have meaningful public and civil society participation](#).

At its simplest, the NDL could support discovery of data held by the public sector that's available for research. It could do this by maintaining a searchable catalogue (or 'index', 'registry', 'portal') of metadata harvested from across many public sector organisations.

In this vein, we've built [Open Net Zero](#) to make net-zero data discoverable, accessible and usable.

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the Open Net Zero website with links for Datasets, Organisations, Request Data, Suggest Data, Documentation, and Become a member. Below this is a main section titled "Net Zero data at your fingertips" with the subtitle "Find, access and securely share net-zero data across industry, environment and finance." A search bar contains the text "Search for data (Finance ~ Energy ~ Water ~ Transport ~ Built World ~ Agriculture)" and a "Search" button. At the bottom, there are three yellow-bordered boxes with call-to-action buttons: "Can't find what you are looking for?" with a "REQUEST DATA" button, "Suggest or submit Open or Commercial data to make it discoverable" with a "SUBMIT LINKS TO DATA" button, and "Support the Icebreaker Principles for net zero data flow" with a "LEARN MORE & SUPPORT" button.

Open Net Zero

Open Net Zero currently indexes metadata on nearly 60,000 datasets from more than 400 organisations' data catalogues. It doesn't copy or store any of the data those organisations hold, but provides a service to help people find relevant datasets wherever they are on the web. This is similar to how existing public data infrastructures such as [data.gov.uk](#), [gov.uk API Catalogue](#) and [Administrative Data Research UK Data Catalogue](#) work. They point to data.

We note that the new [Data for London Library](#) will similarly be "a catalogue to organise the diverse datasets held across London, aiding data users to discover the data they need for their projects.. [including] open data sources relevant to London projects and metadata of private datasets across the public sector and partners". It will initially harvest metadata from across the London Datastore, as well the ONS and London boroughs, before widening to local government bodies, universities and other organisations.

Some data infrastructures also harvest metadata about datasets that can't be made openly available. For example, researchers can discover data available under more restricted technical, legal and commercial conditions via [HDR UK Gateway](#), [Hugging Face Gated Datasets](#) and [Rail Data Marketplace](#), but they must 'click through' these portals and follow the different data holders' access procedures.

While simple, there are still significant [technical challenges](#) to building effective data catalogues. These include:

- *Machine-readability.* Some data catalogues lack a machine-readable interface, which makes our work with Open Net Zero, as a catalogue of catalogues, much harder. We could add 20,000 datasets from a machine-readable catalogue to our index in five minutes, but this isn't generally possible. In many cases, we find that the data publishers have concentrated on building portals for people to manually navigate to find and download a data file, rather than navigate using software.
- *Custom APIs.* We have a backlog of several data catalogues to index that can only be accessed through a custom Application Programming Interface (API). They have an API to list the datasets and retrieve information about them, which is better than nothing, but each API needs to be taken separately. We have to work out how they organised it, how they map to our data structure and so on. This is despite there being established standards for publishing data catalogues, such as [DCAT](#), [CSW](#) and [INSPIRE](#).

- *Standardisation of/around the datasets themselves.* Some catalogues choose only to harvest information about datasets that are published in certain file types or schemas. In operating Open Net Zero, we don't have plans to become a standards body, but we acknowledge that issues such as changing schemas, similar datasets being made available in a variety of file types and inconsistent publication frequencies can make it difficult for users to work with the data downstream.
- *Licensing.* We find licensing of data to be inconsistent and many data portals have no information about what you can do with the data they publish. Some assume it's implicitly open because they've published it on the web, but without an explicit licence we - and prospective data users - can't know that for sure.
- *Recourse.* A lot of organisations put a lot of effort into creating, collating, describing and publishing datasets, but then aren't contactable to help fix issues with their data or help us make improvements to the indexing process.

Early engagement with intended users of this form of NDL would be vital. It could easily be a lame duck, given there are many places where researchers can already find public sector data available for research.

But perhaps this NDL could enable useful new forms of curation of public sector data and data discovery that wouldn't otherwise happen. In health data research, the [seven Health Data Research Hubs initially funded by HDR UK](#) curate data by disease/therapy type, breaking the mould of data catalogues that are generally oriented by sector or around the organisation that collected the data. The data made available by the Hubs is also 'advertised' in different ways on [HDR UK's Gateway](#) and other places on the web. Delivered in the way we describe, the NDL wouldn't preclude other data infrastructures harvesting and presenting the same metadata, serving as one of many entry points for researchers to find public sector data.

What sources should an NDL like this index metadata from? We note that the Technical White Paper Challenge is interested in "key nationally funded data repositories relevant to science and health research in the UK". On this basis, an NDL could work with existing research data infrastructures to develop its 'catalogue of catalogues'.

However, we generally advocate for data infrastructure design to be driven by more specific use cases. In July 2024, DARE UK identified [52 opportunities and societal challenges](#) that could be addressed if the UK's data research infrastructure was better coordinated. ai@cam has recently published [a set of case studies](#) describing the data blockers to undertaking research into topics such as: the diagnosis of ovarian cancer;

the impact of social media on mental health; connecting conservation evidence to policy decision-making; the impacts of climate change; and tracking patterns of economic activity. HM Treasury has published [a list of high level areas of research interest](#). The European Commission [has defined high-value datasets to be made available for reuse](#).

These are the types of use cases the NDL could be designed to curate data to address, and the organisations and communities working to address them should be involved in its design and development.

While feasible, we're conscious that delivering the NDL to aid data discovery wouldn't directly address the most significant challenge facing the use of data for research in the UK: providing researchers with streamlined access to data that is linked or drawn from multiple organisations. The case for this has been made by many, including:

- [Administrative Data Research UK](#): "While other countries allow access to population-level linked data to facilitate research on the drivers of poor health and impacts on economic growth, this is not possible – yet – in the UK. This missed use of data severely constrains the government's ability (both at a UK and devolved levels) to design policies to improve population health and economic outcomes and to evaluate the success of these interventions, limiting evidence-informed decision making across all four UK nations".
- [Public Administration and Constitutional Affairs Committee](#): "Despite the passage of relevant legislation in 2017, the UK has failed to bring its disparate datasets together to enrich its public evidence base. Instead, data withers in silos across countless government bodies. Witnesses to our inquiry were clear; the problems here are not legislative, and they do not result from challenges around data protection. The issue is much simpler; departments and public bodies choose not to share data because they do not share an incentive to do so... Given that the Cabinet Office's existing initiatives for improving data sharing are self-evidently insufficient, it should in partnership with the Office for National Statistics develop a comprehensive new programme aimed at improving data-sharing for statistical and research purposes".
- [Office for Statistics Regulation: State of the Statistical System 2024](#): "Significant progress is still needed in overcoming many of the remaining, often longstanding, barriers to data sharing and linkage. Despite the value of sharing and linking data being widely recognised, and pockets of innovative and ambitious work, there remain areas of challenge... Unless significant changes are implemented, we are concerned the progress that has been made could be lost. We want to see all the parts of the system working together to address these

challenges, to reach a place where sharing and linking datasets, and using them for research and evaluation, is the norm across the UK statistical system, rather than the exception”.

- [Uniting the UK’s Health Data: A Huge Opportunity for Society](#): “Far from being routine, successful linkages of different data sources are all too uncommon, especially those that bring together data from the NHS with data from other sectors, such as census, education or earnings”.

The new [ONS Integrated Data Service](#) is designed to address some of these challenges. But harmonising the different data governance processes used by the government organisations it intends to enable access to data from will be incredibly difficult. Each has a different way of determining who should access the data it holds, as well as an understandable aversion to deferring or pooling responsibility for these decisions.

At IB1, we deliver [Trust Frameworks](#). Trust Frameworks are data infrastructures designed to make data work harder to deliver net zero, primarily by enabling new products, services and markets. [Perseus](#), for example, will help businesses to access over \$100bn of green finance by automating assurable sustainability reporting for every SME in the UK.

In preparing this Technical White Paper, we originally planned to set out a second, more complex technical architecture based on the design of IB1’s Trust Frameworks. It would have been inspired by [Project Sygnus](#), which enabled cloud accounting providers to securely open access to data for research into SME resilience during and after Covid-19. However, doing so ultimately felt too speculative.

[Ben Goldacre’s 2022 review of the UK’s health data](#) identified a wide range of barriers to more effective linkage or combination of data for research. For instance, it argued for UK Government to:

- “Address the problem of 160 trusts and 6,500 GPs all acting as separate data controllers. Do this either through one national organisation acting as Data Controller for a copy of all NHS patients’ records in a TRE, or an ‘approvals pool’ where trusts and GPs can nominate a single entity to review and approve requests on their behalf.”
- “Rationalise approvals: create one map of all approval processes; require all relevant organisations to amend it until all agree it is accurate; de-duplicate work by creating a single common application form (or standard components) for all ethics, information governance, and other access permissions; coordinate

shared meetings when approval requires multiple organisations; have researchers available to address misunderstandings of their project; build institutions to help users who are blocked; recognise and address the risk of data controllers asserting access monopolies to obstruct competitors; publish data on delays annually; ensure high quality patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) is done.”

We suspect that much of the review’s diagnosis and many of the 30 recommendations it made will extrapolate well to the wider research data ecosystem. So rather than propose a technical solution to a systemic challenge, a much broader and deeper set of interventions than the NDL alone will be required if the UK Government’s vision is to harmonise access to data linked or drawn from multiple organisations for research.

5. Important design considerations

There are some significant choices to be made about the NDL regardless of the technical direction it takes.

A. Should the NDL’s scope extend to private sector data?

The UK Industrial Strategy [positions the NDL as a driver of growth](#), by enabling access to “prioritised public data assets... from transport to environmental data”. There are many public sector organisations, and thus a lot of public sector data, that the NDL could support discovery of and/or harmonise access to.

[Onward has said](#) the NDL should also “be open to contributions from archives, universities, and private companies”. However, creating infrastructure that spans the public, private and third sectors is easy to say, but hard to do. There’s a wide field of ideas, initiatives and policies designed to increase access to private sector data for public good, including: [data spaces](#); [data intermediaries](#); [mechanisms for researcher access to platform data](#); [Smart Data Research UK](#); and [data collaboratives](#). The Digital Catapult’s [Data Catalyser](#) sought “to help organisations share data and unlock value for the UK”, before being shut down in 2016.

We feel that many of these approaches fail because they take a ‘build it and they will come’ approach, seeing a deficit of access to data as primarily a technical challenge to overcome. The NDL should avoid this trap, regardless of whether it spans private sector data or not.

B. Will the NDL need a legal mandate?

If the NDL simply aids researchers in discovering data from across government, it probably wouldn't need a legal mandate. It could harvest existing metadata itself, and collaborate with public sector organisations to make available and harvest further metadata. This is potentially a lot of work, but would be possible without legal powers if public organisations see the value of the NDL in driving use of the data they hold.

If the NDL were to take on the more complex task of driving streamlined access to data linked or combined from across multiple public sector organisations, it would more likely require a 'stick' to drive its use and provide appropriate safeguards. The ONS Secure Research Service, for example, is [accredited as a Digital Economy Act 2017 processor by the UK Statistics Authority](#) for the provision of data for research purposes. This compels different parts of government to use the SRS and provides legal safeguards around how the data is used. If the NDL's scope extends to private sector data, then the legal mandates required to drive firms' participation in Open Banking (spanning the CMA/HMT/PSD2) and the National Underground Asset Registry (included in the Data Use and Access Bill) may serve as examples.

C. Will the NDL meet the needs of AI researchers?

Alongside talent and compute, the CMA has recognised [access to data as a necessary condition for a competitive AI market](#). The UK Government has commissioned an [AI Opportunities Action Plan](#) to make sure the UK has "the right AI infrastructure, skills and data access for businesses and public services to unlock its full potential". The NDL has been positioned as 'AI fuel' by organisations such as [UkDayOne](#) ("the National Data Library should leverage the UK's valuable datasets to support areas of competitive advantage in AI") and the [Open Data Institute](#) ("ensure the data assets of the National Data Library can be used effectively and responsibly by AI innovators").

It's difficult to make a hard distinction between AI- and non-AI- research, but it's clear that researchers' needs will vary significantly depending on the purpose, method and intended outputs of their work. Some researchers will look to use the NDL to undertake statistical analysis and data science to produce analytical outputs, using tools such as Python and R. Many of the data infrastructures we list above were originally designed to serve this type of need. But these infrastructures may not support modern AI research. For example, they may not enable researchers to securely train or fine-tune a foundation model (especially across multiple modes of data, linked from across different organisations) using tools such as TensorFlow and PyTorch. For the NDL to be 'AI-ready', or even to decide how much the NDL should index for AI research, a clear vision and grasp of intended users' needs is required.

D. What type of funding with the NDL be built - and crucially, maintained - with?

While appreciating the technical focus of this Challenge, funding data infrastructure effectively is the more significant challenge to overcome than choosing the right architecture. Many sensible people have said this before:

- [Leigh Dodds](#): “A commitment to keep publishing the data.. [is] what makes data infrastructure. The commitment, not the technology”.
- [Jeni Tennison](#): “Data services need to be sustainable and scalable, which means having permanent multidisciplinary teams and sustainable budget lines. They should not be one-off projects that fall by the wayside when political interest moves on.”
- [Ellie Ashman](#): “For any piece of national data infrastructure to be a success, it needs to be.. funded like a permanent fixture, whilst also being funded as the complex space it is - with a skilled team and adaptive practices at the centre”.
- [Gavin Starks](#): “Work out how to prioritise and create clear (and stable) roadmaps that enable investment to be made”.
- [Jennifer Pahlka](#): “Product > project funding”.
- [David Thomas](#): “Let's fund teams, not projects”.
- [Cathie Sudlow](#): “Long-term investment in national [health] data infrastructure is needed, rather than short-term initiatives with unrealistic timelines for delivery”.

According to [Whong's Law](#), every government agency, everywhere, is working on a new system that'll solve all data problems and will be ready to use in 18-24 months. Except it will *always* be ready in 18-24 months. To avoid conforming to this, an effective NDL will require flexible, long term funding. The technical architecture won't matter if this isn't the case.